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ABSTRACT

We report on the epitaxial growth, theoretical modeling, and structural as well as optical investigation of multi-layer, site-controlled quantum dots fabricated using the buried stressor method. This deterministic growth technique utilizes the strain from a partially oxidized AlAs layer to induce site-selective nucleation of InGaAs quantum dots. By implementing strain-induced spectral nano-engineering, we achieve spectral control of emission and a local increase in the emitter density. Furthermore, we achieve a threefold increase in the optical intensity and reduce the inhomogeneous broadening of the ensemble emission by 20% via stacking three layers of site-controlled emitters, which is valuable for using the SCQDs as a gain medium in microlaser applications. Our optimization of site-controlled growth of quantum dots enables the development of high- β microlasers with increased confinement factor.

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The scalability of nanophotonic systems is a key to unlocking their full potential and realizing their widespread applications in various fields, such as optoelectronics and emerging photonic quantum information technologies based on single quantum emitters.^{1–3} Furthermore, the emission properties of cavity-enhanced microlasers are also improved by a controlled integration of quasi-zero-dimensional gain centers.⁴ In this regard, the deterministic fabrication of nanophotonic devices with a controlled number and position of semiconductor quantum dots (QDs) is an important step forward in achieving that goal. In the last two decades, innovative methods to control the position of QDs have been developed, including the usage of etched nanoholes, pre-patterned substrates, and cleaved-edge overgrowth.^{5–12} Another attractive growth approach for site-controlled QDs (SCQDs) is the buried stressor method.^{13,14} This deterministic growth technique leads to high-quality SCQDs with narrow emission linewidth and high multi-photon suppression as well as pronounced

resonance fluorescence.¹⁵ In this method the stressor layer below the growth surface is used to control the nucleation site, and local number of the QDs.^{13,14} This allows for the deterministic and scalable fabrication of single-photon sources (SPSs)¹⁶ and high- β micropillar lasers.¹⁷ However, despite its proven potential, systematic studies on the employment of the buried-stressor method for the optimization of site-controlled QDs (SCQDs) for usage as a gain medium in microlasers are still lacking.

Here, we report on the investigation of the buried stressor growth method to engineer the QD gain medium for increasing the confinement (Γ) and β -factors of microcavity lasers, while at the same time reducing the absorption losses due to non-positioned QDs. This paves the way to the energy-efficient operation of those devices, which is of great interest, for instance, in photonic reservoir computing, where hundreds of microlasers need to be pumped above threshold.^{18,19} Furthermore, we show that the buried stressor technique could serve

as an alternative approach for growing high-quality QDs emitting prospectively in the telecom O-band, to complement existing non-positioning methods, such as strain-reducing layers (SRLs) and metamorphic buffer layers (MB).^{20,21}

The buried stressor method takes advantage of the strain induced by a partially oxidized AlAs layer, stemming from a lattice constant difference between AlAs (5.660 Å) and Al₂O₃ (4.785 Å). The resulting tensile strain at the center of the etched mesa protrudes to the surface, where it leads to the accumulation of indium atoms at the most tensile strained positions (largest lattice constant) above the aperture, which results in the site-controlled nucleation of QDs.¹⁴ In addition, control over the emission wavelength is achieved by optimizing the growth interruption time. To further increase the optical gain for laser applications, we stack multiple layers of SCQD (ML-SCQDs). Compared to conventional SK QDs, the stacking of SCQDs results in higher optical gain and better spectral homogeneity, as well as positional control of QD formation.²²

Our samples were fabricated through a two-step growth process using metal-organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD). After the first growth step, UV-lithography was employed to pattern an array of square mesas with approximately 20 μm side length. These mesas were subsequently dry-etched to expose the AlAs layer, which was then selectively oxidized to create the AlAs aperture at the mesa's center, before performing the second growth step of the site-controlled QDs. The layer design and process steps are displayed in the supplementary material Fig. S1. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) was employed to investigate the strain profile at the QD growth surface and to measure the QD density. The microscopic analysis is complemented by Raman spectroscopy above the aperture, which is used to monitor the strain profile by measuring the strain-induced spectral shift of the longitudinal optical phonon (LO) line of GaAs. Moreover, we applied the finite-difference method to simulate the strength and shape of induced stress and its effect on the SCQDs using continuum elasticity theory.²³ Finally, high-resolution cathodoluminescence (CL) was utilized to characterize the emission properties of the emitters. Our approach allows us to shift the energy of the site-controlled emitters compared to the non-positioned QDs, enabling, thus, the growth of SCQD with high density without compromising the site-controlled nature of the buried stressor technique. Moreover, compared to non-positioned QDs, we enhance the optical gain threefold while reducing the inhomogeneous broadening of the ensemble by stacking three layers of SCQDs.

We first discuss the growth and emission properties of a single layer of SCQDs. Figure 1(a) shows a CL intensity color map of a single layer of SCQDs with a growth interruption time of 40 s in the wavelength range between 1000 and 1150 nm overlapped with an SEM image of the mesa, demonstrating high position accuracy (below 100 nm) of the buried stressor method. Noteworthy, while SCQDs based on nanohole arrays and inverted pyramids feature an alignment accuracy in the tens of nm and are suitable for integration into photonic crystal cavities,^{24,25} buried stressor SCQDs, with usually better optical properties, are more suitable for integration in high Q-factor cavities with relaxed mode-matching requirements on the order of a few 100 nm. CL emission of on- and off-aperture positions from the mesa shown in Fig. 1(a) is displayed in Fig. 1(b). The SCQDs have a maximum emission wavelength of 1070 nm [red curve in Fig. 1(b)] and exhibit a strongly redshifted emission in comparison with the non-positioned QDs of 950 nm [blue curve in Fig. 1(b)]. For

comparison, the wetting layer emission occurs at 920 nm (see the supplementary material, Fig. S2). The shift of the emission wavelength is achieved by higher localized tensile surface strain above the aperture combined with a longer growth interruption (of 40 s as discussed below) time. The observed magnitude of the redshift is compatible with an increased indium content in the SCQDs as well as with larger QDs. We interpret the observed behavior by buried stressor-induced migration of the indium atoms to the most tensile strained position directly above the aperture, resulting in a higher indium concentration in the center of the mesa. This together with a higher InGaAs growth rate, hence, leads to an increase in the density, size, and indium content of SCQDs compared to non-positioned QDs, thus contributing to the observed redshift of SCQD emission. Intriguing, apart from the achieved spectral redshift, the peak intensity of the SCQDs is maintained compared to the non-positioned QDs. We attribute that to the high quality of the growth surface and low defect density compared to other methods for redshifting QD emission using a SRL or a MB.

To obtain better insight into the buried stressor growth of SCQDs, the surface strain distribution at the growth surface was modeled using the continuum elasticity theory. Simulations of the strain profile at the GaAs surface vs the position on the mesa for different aperture sizes are depicted in Fig. 1(c). The difference in lattice constants between AlAs and Al₂O₃ results in lateral strain, which propagates in the growth direction to the surface [see the supplementary material, Figs. S3(a) and S3(b)], where the InGaAs wetting layer is deposited. The buried stressor creates tensile and compressive stress with surface strain extrema of 0.4% and -0.12%, respectively. The strain profile depends in this configuration solely on the size of the aperture as seen in Fig. 1(c) (see the supplementary material, Fig. S4), whereas the strain magnitude depends on the size of the aperture as can be observed in Fig. 1(c), the stressor layer thickness, and the aperture to surface distance [see the supplementary material, Fig. S6(a)]. Corresponding AFM measurements in Fig. 1(d) show a smooth height profile after the growth of a single uncapped QD layer for different aperture sizes. Here, the migration of indium atoms from the compressive to the tensile position leads to a change in the growth rate directly above and surrounding the aperture. As shown in Fig. 1(d), this results in a thickness difference in the growth direction, whereas the unstrained GaAs on the mesa remains unchanged. We denote the height difference between most tensile positions located above the aperture and the GaAs surface as Δ_t , a parameter that characterizes the magnitude of the strain-induced growth rate change above the stressor. As predicted by simulations, the smallest aperture exhibits the highest Δ_t due to an increase in the surface strain with a smaller aperture size. As the compressively strained position is depleted of indium, no QD growth is observed in related areas in the AFM images (see the supplementary material, Fig. S4). Indium atoms that migrate to the nearby tensile strained positions above the aperture result in SCQDs with higher indium content, which explains the redshift of the SCQD emission in Fig. 1(b). The associated lack of QD growth around the aperture can also be observed in the CL maps [see white ring surrounding the aperture in Fig. 1(a) right], as the luminescence from the surrounding area of the aperture is weak to non-existent.

The strain distribution is monitored by measuring the Raman emission in the surrounding GaAs above the unoxidized AlAs layer. For this purpose, we performed systematic Raman spectroscopy measurements. A corresponding color map of the GaAs LO-phonon

FIG. 1. Optical and strain analysis of SCQDs. (a) Low temperature (20 K) CL intensity map of SCQD emission ranging from 1000 to 1150 nm is overlaid with an SEM image of the quadratic mesa, including the crystallographic orientation of the mesa edges. The high position accuracy of the growth technique is visually demonstrated by the presence of two yellow dotted lines. Inset: Zoom-in CL image taken at the center of the mesa. (b) The CL spectrum is shown in red and blue for the center and off-center regions of the mesa at 20 K, respectively. (c) Calculated surface strain profile $\varepsilon_{xx} + \varepsilon_{yy}$ along the cross section of the mesa, as a function of the aperture size. $\varepsilon_{xx} + \varepsilon_{yy} = 0$ corresponds to unstrained GaAs. (d) AFM height profile of the aperture for various aperture sizes. (e) Strain taken at the center of the mesa, obtained by Raman measurements. (f) A line cut to the center of the mesa of the Raman map in (e) for three different aperture sizes (800, 1100, and 1900 nm).

Raman band recomputed to strain for a mesa with an aperture size of approximately 1000 nm is shown in Fig. 1(e). The stressor-induced surface strain change is associated with a change in the bond lengths, resulting in a shift of the GaAs LO-phonon band, in this case resulting in a Raman shift of approximately 1.7 cm^{-1} , corresponding to a strain magnitude of $(0.350 \pm 0.001)\%$. The induced strain is evident in the line scans displayed in Fig. 1(f) for three different-sized apertures. The noteworthy observation in this context is the excellent quantitative agreement between the computed strain (approximately 0.3%) and the measured strain $[(0.350 \pm 0.001)\%]$, as evident in Figs. 1(c) and 1(f). This substantiates the predictive nature of the simulation.

Next, we study the stacking multiple QD layers using the buried stressor method. In Fig. 2(a), we present the AFM height profiles at the center of the mesa for one, two, and three layers of SCQD structures with similar aperture sizes (approximately $2 \mu\text{m}$). We observe that stacking of multiple QD layers does not alter the overall shape of the surface strain profile and that QDs in the upper layers are aligned by the strain field of buried stressor as well (see, e.g., Fig. S5). However, the height difference Δ_t between the most tensile and compressive positions increases systematically with the number of deposited QD layers, as indicated by the red data points in Fig. 2(b). The gradual increase in Δ_t with the number of QD layers is attributed to the larger tensile strain due to the increased distance between the aperture and

FIG. 2. Properties of multi-layer SCQDs. (a) Line scan of AFM measurements, presenting the height profile for a varying number of SCQD layers at the center of the mesa with similar aperture sizes (approximately $2 \mu\text{m}$), relative to the GaAs surface. (b) Emission wavelength of the SCQDs (black data points) relative to the number of deposited emitter layers and height difference (red data points) between the most tensile and compressive positions in the center of the mesa. (c) The CL emission spectra exhibit inhomogeneous broadening for different numbers of stacked layers, including the wetting layer (red), non-positioned QDs (blue), and SCQDs (black). (d) The integrated CL intensity is plotted against the number of grown layers, revealing enhanced intensity with increased layer stacking.

SCQD layer in addition to the accumulation of the indium, which persists across the multiple layers. Therefore, the growth of multiple layers and the stress induced by the QDs do not seem to modify the surface strain profile significantly, except of an approximately 0.7% change in the absolute surface strain between the first and the third layer due to the larger distance from the aperture. However, we do not expect any significant effects on the formation of SCQDs, which is confirmed by the constant QD density distribution observed across the layers [see the supplementary material, Figs. S5 and S6(b)].

To evaluate the optical properties of the QDs, we fit the spectra obtained from CL measurements, as shown in Fig. 1(b), by a Gaussian function, across multiple mesas and variations in the number of layers. In Fig. 2(b), we present the corresponding emission wavelength of the SCQDs. Notably, we observed a distinct blue shift in the emission when two layers were stacked, reducing the wavelength from (1059 ± 10) nm for a single layer to (1027 ± 22) nm for the two-layer structure. This shift can be attributed to a decrease in the average height of the QDs in the second layer analogous to standard SK QDs.²² Furthermore, Fig. 2(c) demonstrates a similar trend regarding the inhomogeneous broadening of the non-positioned and SCQDs, which decreases with the number of layers from (80 ± 13) nm and (43 ± 6) nm in the first layer to (67 ± 9) nm and (28 ± 3) nm for

positioned and non-positioned QDs, respectively, indicating improved uniformity of QD sizes because of strain-coupling.²²

The stacking of SCQDs also results in a nearly linear increase in integrated CL intensity, as shown in Fig. 2(d). The intensity in Fig. 2(d) does not show saturation, which shows that the high optical quality of the emitters is preserved during the stacking.

Interestingly, the buried stressor method also provides an attractive opportunity to redshift the emission of SCQD. For example, consider the strain magnitude or, more precisely, the shift in the GaAs LO band associated with an aperture size of 1000 nm. The corresponding Raman frequency shift is approximately 1.65 cm^{-1} , a value comparable to that of an $\text{In}_{0.15}\text{Ga}_{0.85}\text{As}$ MB layer with a thickness ranging from approximately 40–50 nm.²⁶ To demonstrate the strain-engineered redshifting of SCQD emission, we utilize the buried stressor-induced strain profile above the aperture. Here, the additional tensile strain in the center of the mesa leads to energetically lower QD equilibrium compared to the unstrained surface. Second, by increasing the growth interruption time, we allow for the SCQDs to accumulate more indium atoms, resulting in bigger dots with increased indium concentration and a corresponding 70 nm redshift of the emission as seen in Fig. 3(a). The blue (red) spectrum represents a sample prepared with a growth interruption time after the deposition of InGaAs of 20 (40) s. Additionally, our numerical

FIG. 3. Strain engineering the emission wavelength of SCQDs. (a) CL spectra of two similar structures containing SCQDs are shown. The blue (red) spectrum corresponds to QDs obtained with a growth interruption time of 20 (40) s. (b) The CL emission from a structure with 40 s of growth interruption time for two aperture sizes. Increasing the size of the aperture reduces the tensile surface strain, leading to a blue shift in the emission. (c) The experimental peak position of the emission for the SCQDs (black data points) and the numerical results. The theory results are provided for the surface strain at the center of mesa (green squares) and for maximum surface strain on the aperture (khaki squares). (d) Examples of CL line scans displaying the emission properties above the aperture for various aperture sizes are shown, with the red line serving as a reference to facilitate the observation of the blue shift resulting from the increased aperture size.

studies predict that the tensile strain induced by the aperture will further redshift the emission [see the supplementary material, Fig. S7(a)]. Note that in the calculations, the surface strain obtained from the continuum elasticity theory is added to the as-grown QD strain during the $k\cdot p$ computation.^{27,28} The increase in the aperture size results in a weaker lateral strain between AIAs and Al_2O_3 , which in turn decreases the stress propagation to the surface. The increased magnitude of the tensile strain at the center of the mesa due to the reduction of the aperture size results in larger QDs with increased indium content, leading to a redshift of 70 nm in the emission of the SCQDs, as depicted in Fig. 3(b). In Fig. 3(c), the experimental and theoretical emission wavelengths are plotted against the aperture size. In both graphs, the emission wavelength is highest for the smallest aperture size and then drops rapidly with increasing aperture size. That is due to the reduction in surface strain with a bigger unoxidized AIAs region. Consequently, the migration of indium atoms and an increase in growth rate above the aperture occur. The discussed dependencies are also reflected in the CL line scans of apertures with varying sizes, as presented in Fig. 3(d). Apertures of 930, 1700, and 5300 nm in width result in peak emission wavelengths of 1070, 1010, and 985 nm, respectively. In order to shift the emission

toward the telecom O-band, we suggest that a thicker AIAs stressor layer and a top GaAs spacer, leading to an increased tensile surface strain, and associated increase in Indium content in QDs should be used.

In summary, we introduced an innovative approach based on the buried stressor technique, to achieve a redshift of SCQDs relative to non-positioned ones. This approach enables the deposition of high-density SCQDs within a singular layer, preserving excellent positional control. This is achieved while concurrently monitoring and simulating strain distribution to gain deeper insights into the underlying mechanisms. Furthermore, we demonstrate the stacking of three SCQD layers, resulting in a threefold increase in optical intensity and a reduction in ensemble inhomogeneous broadening. Subsequently, we investigate the strain-induced redshift of the SCQD ensemble, granting us direct control over emission properties. Combining the buried stressor technique with strain nano-engineering of emission provides control over the site, number/density, and optical properties of both ensembles and single QDs. This achievement can potentially pave the way not only for high- β factor and low-threshold microlasers, but also for single-photon sources operating in the O-band without the need of a conventional strain reducing layer.

See the supplementary material for details regarding fabrication, characterization, and simulation methods, as well as additional optical, structural, and simulation results.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Imad Limame: Conceptualization (equal). **Petr Klenovský:** Funding acquisition (supporting). **Stephan Reitzenstein:** Supervision (lead). **Ching-Wen Shih:** Investigation (equal). **Alexej Koltchanov:** Data curation (equal). **Fabian Heisinger:** Data curation (supporting). **Felix Nippert:** Formal analysis (supporting). **Moritz Plattner:** Data curation (supporting). **Johannes Schall:** Methodology (supporting). **Markus R. Wagner:** Supervision (supporting). **Sven Rodt:** Methodology (supporting).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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